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FROM FUN TO WRITTEN LANGUAGE: BUILDING PHONOLOGICAL AWARENESS IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF MANGARATIBA/RJ

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ABSTRACT

THE project of search proposed will focus in the education childish, specifically in the range children aged 4 and 5 in the municipality of Mangaratiba, with an emphasis on the development of phonological awareness. Since 2017, the preschool in question has implemented practices to stimulate phonological awareness skills, including awareness of words, syllables, rhymes, alliteration and phonemes, all practiced orally. The goal is to prepare children for literacy, providing a solid foundation before advancing to elementary school. The research will adopt a qualitative methodology, conducting a study with a small group of teachers from the preschool network through group focal. This approach will allow an in-depth analysis of how the stimulation of phonological awareness is being conducted, in addition to identifying challenges and results of this educational process.

KEYWORDS: Phonological awareness; early childhood education; methodology qualitative.